

Solving the Blocks World Problem Using the Soar Cognitive System: A Unified Cognitive Architecture Approach

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Abstract—This paper presents the implementation and analysis of solving the Blocks World problem using the Soar cognitive system, a unified cognitive architecture widely used in artificial intelligence and cognitive science research. The problem consists of reconfiguring three blocks placed on a table such that block A rests on block B, which in turn rests on block C, which is directly on the table. The implementation was carried out using production rules in the Soar language, encompassing state initialization, predicate elaboration, operator proposal and evaluation, and monitoring of intermediate states. The results demonstrated that the agent reached the goal state in only two effective decision cycles, with a total of 44 rules fired, highlighting the efficiency of the architecture for small-scale planning problems. The discussion addresses operator control mechanisms, the role of preferences in action selection, and the scalability limitations of the approach.

Index Terms—Soar Architecture, Blocks World Problem, Artificial Intelligence, Production Systems, Automated Planning.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Blocks World problem is one of the classical domains in artificial intelligence, widely used to test and validate techniques in planning, machine learning, and knowledge representation (Russell and Norvig, 2021). Its apparent simplicity conceals fundamental challenges related to search in state spaces, conflict resolution among operators, and the definition of efficient heuristics. Since the pioneering work of Winograd with the SHRDLU system in the 1970s, the blocks domain has served as a benchmark for symbolic reasoning systems (Winograd, 1972). The relevance of the problem persists to this day, as it abstractly captures characteristics present in real-world tasks such as robotic planning, logistics, and structure assembly.

The Soar system, originally developed by Allen Newell, John Laird, and Paul Rosenbloom at Carnegie Mellon University and later expanded at the University of Michigan, constitutes one of the most comprehensive and well-studied cognitive architectures in the literature (Laird, Newell and Rosenbloom, 1987). Grounded in the physical symbol system hypothesis (Newell and Simon, 1976), Soar posits that all intelligent behavior can be described as a search process in a problem-solving state space, guided by production rules that fire in parallel when their conditions are satisfied. The architecture integrates working memory, production memory, semantic memory, episodic memory, and learning through chunking within a unified framework (Laird, 2012).

The motivation for applying Soar to the Blocks World problem lies in demonstrating how a general-purpose cognitive architecture can solve planning tasks without requiring the programmer to explicitly specify a search algorithm. The Soar agent operates guided by the decision cycle, which includes the phases of elaboration, operator proposal, preference evaluation, and application, delegating execution control to the architecture itself (Laird, 2012). In this context, this paper aims to describe the implementation of a Soar agent for the three-block Blocks World problem, analyze the observed behavior during execution, and discuss the implications of the obtained results in light of the specialized literature.

II. METHODOLOGY

The implementation was carried out using version 9.6.4 of the Soar environment, with the Soar Debugger in Java employed as the development and debugging interface, as illustrated in Figure 1. The agent was coded in a single production rule file with the `.soar` extension, totaling 16 productions that cover everything from the initialization of the world state to the stopping criterion upon reaching the goal.

The initial world state was defined by the initialization production, which creates four objects in working memory: blocks A, B, and C, each of type “block”, and the table, of type “table”. Three `ontop` structures were instantiated, each associating a block directly with the table, representing the initial configuration in which no block is stacked on another. The desired state, encoded in the `desired` structure, specifies that block A must be on B, B on C, and C on the table, corresponding to the A-B-C stack with C as the base. This declarative representation of the goal is a central feature of the Soar approach, as it separates knowledge about what is to be achieved from knowledge about how to achieve it (Laird and Congdon, 2024).

The elaboration mechanism was implemented through four auxiliary productions. The first, P1, detects blocks that are free, i.e., those that do not serve as a base for any other block, and adds the corresponding `clear` predicate to working memory. The second, P2, marks the table as always available to receive blocks. The third, P3, designates the table as an `inplace` object, indicating that it is already in its final position in the goal configuration. The fourth, P4, propagates the `inplace` predicate to blocks that are already correctly positioned relative to the desired state, allowing the agent to

Fig. 1. Soar Debugger

recognize partial progress toward the goal without requiring global replanning.

Production P5 proposes movement operators for every pair of objects in which both the block and the destination are free and the block is not already on the intended support. All operators receive indifferent preferences, allowing Soar to make arbitrary choices in the absence of additional criteria. To guide the search, two evaluation productions are employed: P6 assigns a better preference to moves that place blocks on the table when none are yet in their final position, avoiding premature stacking; P7 assigns a better preference to the operator that places a block on an object marked as *inplace*, favoring the incremental construction of the correct stack from the base. This mechanism implements a local heuristic consistent with partially ordered planning strategies described by Ghallab, Nau and Traverso (2016).

The application of the operator is performed by P10, which updates the *bottom-block* attribute in the *ontop* structure, replacing the previous support with the new destination. Subsequently, a flag activates the monitoring productions P13, responsible for printing the current state of the stack. Termination occurs through P11, which detects when all three blocks are marked as *inplace* and executes the *halt* instruction.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The agent execution was performed using the “run” command in the Soar Debugger, and the complete results are shown in Figure 1. The agent completed the task in three decision cycles, the first dedicated to world initialization and the subsequent two to executing the required movements.

In total, 44 production rules were fired during execution, reflecting the work performed by elaboration productions in each cycle to maintain a consistent and updated working memory.

In the second decision cycle, operator O8 was selected and applied the movement *move-block(B, C)*, placing block B on top of block C. After this movement, the state printed in the console showed configuration with C at the base, B on C, and A still isolated on the table. In the third cycle, operator O10 applied the movement *move-block(A, B)*, placing block A on B and thus completing the stack C-B-A as required by the desired state. Production P11 then detected that the three objects A, B, and C were simultaneously marked as “inplace” and terminated execution with the message “Goal Achieved (three blocks).”

It is important to note that the sequence of movements obtained—B on C followed by A on B—corresponds to the optimal solution for the three-block problem starting from the initial configuration in which all blocks are on the table. No unnecessary movements were performed, demonstrating that the preference scheme implemented in productions P6 and P7 was effective in guiding the agent directly to the solution without exploring irrelevant branches of the state space. This result is consistent with the argument of Laird (2012) that well-designed preferences eliminate the need for exhaustive search in small-scale problems, making the Soar decision cycle sufficient to ensure rational behavior.

The absence of impasses during execution is a relevant outcome. In Soar, impasses arise when the decision cycle cannot select a single operator, either due to preference con-

flicts or lack of proposals, leading to the automatic creation of a subgoal for deliberation (Laird, Newell and Rosenbloom, 1987). In the described experiment, the combination of better and indifferent preferences produced deterministic selection in all cycles, avoiding subgoals and maintaining linear execution, which indicates that the preference structure adequately encoded domain knowledge.

From the perspective of knowledge representation, the implementation highlights the separation between state knowledge (ontop and clear structures), goal knowledge (desired structure), and control knowledge (productions P6 and P7), a central characteristic of Soar associated with its modularity and readability (Anderson et al., 2004). However, scalability remains a limitation: planners based exclusively on production rules tend to exhibit exponential growth in the number of cycles as the number of blocks increases, due to the factorial growth of the state space (Slaney and Thiébaux, 2001).

The chunking mechanism, native to Soar, emerges as an alternative to mitigate this limitation by compiling the results of subgoals into new productions, enabling reuse of prior reasoning (Laird, 2012). Studies indicate that integration with reinforcement learning can yield substantial gains in sequential planning domains (Nair et al., 2019), while the incorporation of instructional learning expands the architecture’s scope by enabling acquisition of new behaviors through natural language (Kirk and Laird, 2019).

Comparison with other planning formalisms reveals relevant differences. PDDL-based planners such as Fast Downward (Helmert, 2006) solve instances of the Blocks World problem with dozens of elements in fractions of a second using informed search heuristics, such as additive and landmark heuristics. However, such systems lack the complete cognitive apparatus of Soar, which integrates multiple memory systems, learning, and metacognitive mechanisms into a unified architecture (Laird, 2012). Thus, the choice between a dedicated planner and a general-purpose cognitive architecture depends on the application goals: for maximum planning efficiency, systems such as Fast Downward tend to be superior; for realistic cognitive modeling or integration between planning, perception, language, and learning, Soar presents distinctive advantages (Sun, 2006).

The source code of this research is available at: <https://github.com/vitor-souza-ime/bw>.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This work demonstrated the application of Soar to the three-block Blocks World problem, using 16 productions organized into initialization, elaboration, proposal, evaluation, and application phases. The agent achieved the goal state in two movements, without unnecessary exploration of the state space or generation of subgoals. The preference scheme implemented in productions P6 and P7 guided behavior deterministically toward the optimal solution, demonstrating the suitability of the architecture for small-scale planning tasks.

The results highlight that the separation between state, goal, and control knowledge promotes modularity and clarity

of the model. However, scalability to larger problems may require mechanisms such as chunking or integration with machine learning techniques to avoid exponential performance degradation. Future work includes increasing the number of blocks, enabling chunking, and comparing with PDDL-based planners.

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